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INCREMENTALLY-MAINTAINED MATERIALIZED VIEWS IN APPLICATIONS WITH RELATIONAL DBMSes AND THE EFFICIENCY OF THEIR USE

Abstract.

This paper explores the use of incrementally maintained materialized views (IMMV) in enterprise applications. The objective of the research is to evaluate the performance of IMMVs and identify their advantages and disadvantages using the database schema of an online marketplace as a case study. In order to achieve this, a database schema and several IMMVs were created in PostgreSQL, and an incremental update mechanism was implemented in Python. Transaction processing times and query-execution speeds were then measured. The results of the experiment indicate that, as the number of IMMVs increases, transaction processing time grows linearly, whereas data retrieval from materialized views is substantially accelerated – by more than a factor of thirty in some cases – and remains constant regardless of data volume. The paper presents graphs illustrating the relationship between transaction processing time and the number of IMMVs involved. A comparison of execution times for base queries and their corresponding IMMVs is also presented in this paper. We also analyze practical analytics monitoring scenarios – such as computing a customer’s average order value or total monthly sales – demonstrating that IMMVs provide rapid access to results compared with re-executing the base queries. Key benefits of IMMVs include significant increase of speed for the data retrieval and the maintenance of query result freshness upon updates of base tables. However, the use of IMMVs introduces disadvantages such as degraded transaction processing speed, increased system complexity, tighter component coupling, and reduced fault tolerance due to potential update errors. In conclusion, the adoption of IMMVs is advisable only when workload characteristics – namely frequent or complex read queries – justify the trade-offs. Segregating OLTP and OLAP functions is recommended where appropriate. Future work will focus on developing tools for the automated management of IMMVs and on exploring their applications across diverse domains.

Keywords: materialized views, enterprise applications, relational databases, transactions, IMMV, decision-making, OLAP

Introduction

Relational databases (hereinafter referred to as DBs) are frequently used in modern enterprise applications to store information. This is due to their ACID properties (Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, and Durability) provided by a mathematical data model based on a large number of theorems, data integrity, and query language. This allows several relational database management systems (RDBMS), such as Oracle [1] or PostgreSQL [2], to develop and gain widespread adoption.

Queries are used to retrieve data from DBs. The execution of selection queries in an RDBMS generates result sets, which are collections of tuples with a uniform structure. Therefore, they can be stored in some tables.

The open-source RDBMS PostgreSQL uses the ANSI SQL standard for query language. According to this standard, selection queries are constructed using the SELECT statement. Also, views are defined as virtual tables created from the result set of a selection query.

A view in PostgreSQL is a table that is not physically stored and has an ON SELECT DO INSTEAD rule. Rather than querying the table directly, this rule

executes a stored query that retrieves data from the base tables of this view.

Views allow queries to be named. This enables querying views alongside with the regular tables, which leads to simplification of queries and enhancement of the data security by granting access to specific views for privileged users. Views are mainly used to create a logical abstraction level over physical DB tables. View level is the third (external) level of the ANSI-SPARC three-level architecture.

A table of materialized view (MV) is stored physically, unlike the table of a regular view. MVs also have a rule that ensures the view is saved upon its creation after execution of the selection query. This query is called the base query of MV. The base query may reference one or more existing tables, which are considered the base tables for this MV.

Unlike views, MVs not only allow selection queries to be named, but also allow result sets of these queries to be cached. This introduces the possibility of speeding up query execution by storing the results of some calculations in the MV. The use of MVs in this case is an example of a space-time trade-off.

An important task when working with MVs is their timely and optimal updating. Timeliness refers to

the consistency between the data in the MV and the data in its base tables. Optimality, in turn, refers to an MV update strategy that minimizes the number of required operations for that update.

There are several MV update techniques that meet the criteria of timeliness and optimality. These include the FAST refresh for MVs in Oracle [3] and the Incremental View Maintenance (IVM) technique for MVs in PostgreSQL [4]. MVs that are incrementally updated using the IVM technique are referred to as Incrementally Maintainable Materialized Views (IMMV).

Research on the necessity of using IMMV has a significant relevance in general and specific cases. Indeed, if data retrieval from IMMV accelerates program execution, it can reduce server maintenance costs. The case of development the automated tools for generating database applications is provided in [5]. That tool was built on the foundation of MVs. Therefore, the results of studies on the MVs usage tactics will significantly contribute to the creation of a modern tool similar to [5].

The research has the following key attributes:

Methodology – experimental research of a sufficient fragment of the schema of an industrial DB schema, which aims to obtain improved query execution time.

Experiment – automatic measurement of query execution times and representation of the results in graphical form for further analysis.

Research concept – updating the results tested in [5] on a modern trending RDBMS.

In works [6, 7], as well as in the related theoretical research, theorems have been mathematically proven, showing that for DB schemas free from multivalued dependency and projection-join dependency (MVD-PJD) [8] all characteristics are similar. Therefore, whether analyzing thousands of relations with billions of tuples or just ten relations with hundreds of thousands of rows, the proportionality of measurement results will not be affected. Consequently, the work investigates a fragment of a schema implemented in an industrial DB. Therefore, the results presented here can be reproduced multiple times, and given the average error, they remain consistent. The average error in execution time of 1%, measured over 100 trials, can be ignored.

Authors believe that, based on the described concept, new scientific results have been obtained. A

literature review performed reveals no publication where this approach to research was specifically addressed. However, the approach described here can be used for the development of new methods for automating DB application programming, as described in [5].

The work [9] shows that when using a DB schema free of the aforementioned anomalies [6-8] to develop data warehouses (DW) based on IMMV and to conduct analytical research on them, it is not necessary to perform additional restructuring of the schema of the implemented database. In addition, the use of join operations is minimized in applications with such DW's, since IMMV are tables that have already been prepared by joining at the OLTP stage. Therefore, at the OLAP stage, i.e., in the DW mode, applications predominantly use only select operations. This property of IMMV also proves the correctness and significant relevance of the research conducted.

Thus, using the marketplace application as an example, we will analyze the task of constructing analytical data through incrementally maintained MVs. For this purpose, we will assess the impact of the mentioned MVs on transaction processing times and the time it takes to retrieve analytical data from the DB using index tables. We will enumerate the cases when using IMMV is beneficial and outline the advantages and disadvantages of using IMMVs.

Problem formulation

Let us consider a fragment of the schema of an online marketplace DB. It consists of five tables containing data about manufacturers, products, buyers, orders, and products in orders. As it was noted in [6-8], tables free from MVD-PJD are in 5NF. Therefore, they adhere to industry best practices. The tables were constructed using:

- UUIDv4 [10] as primary keys;
- Foreign keys to ensure referential integrity between tables;
- Constraints that reduce the permissible value sets (data types or domains) for table columns. For example, the product price cannot be negative, and a manufacturer cannot have two products with the same name.

Figure 1 shows the ER diagram with Crow's Foot notation [11] of the schema's described fragment.

Fig. 1. ER diagram of a fragment of the online marketplace database schema

Then, let us consider the following MVs:

1. The total amount of money for sold goods each month for each manufacturer;
2. The total amount of money for purchased goods each month for each buyer;
3. The number of units of each product sold each month;
4. The total number of units of each product sold overall;
5. The average order amount for each buyer overall;
6. The average order amount for each buyer each month;
7. The total amount of money spent on goods from each manufacturer by each buyer each month.

It is necessary to:

1. Determine how MVs incremental updates affect transaction processing time;
2. Compare the speed of data retrieval using the base query for the MV and from the MV itself;
3. Identify the cases when incremental update of the MV is more beneficial than execution of the base query for the MV.

Progress of the computational experiment

In order to perform the computational experiment, Docker containers with PostgreSQL 17.4 RDBMS and an application written in Python 3.13 were deployed on a computer with an Intel Core i3 processor (4 cores at 3.00 GHz each). `asyncpg` [12], as the fastest asynchronous Python client for PostgreSQL, was used to interact with PostgreSQL.

PostgreSQL's built-in functionality only supports full MV refresh via the `REFRESH MATERIALIZED VIEW` command. The IVM technique is currently implemented only through third-party solutions – both open-source (`pg_ivm` [13]) and proprietary (Epsio [14], Materialize [15]).

Such software does not use the built-in PostgreSQL MV implementation. Instead, they contain their own MV implementation. For example, `pg_ivm` instead of utilization of built-in MV creates a standard

table and adds AFTER triggers to all base tables. As a result, whenever a base table is updated, incremental changes are propagated to the table acting as the MV.

The use of third-party solutions for incremental MV updates should be justified enough, as it may lead to excessive engineering. Therefore, at the early stages of application development, for simplicity and ease of testing, it is advisable to implement incremental MV updates in the client (application) code, which was done in this experiment.

The first stage of the experiment involved filling the tables with random data and measuring transaction processing times.

Measurement consisted of the following steps:

1. The data from all tables was removed with `TRUNCATE` operation.
2. Then, the tables with constant data (which would not change during the experiment) were populated with data about manufacturers, products, and customers. The `Faker` Python package, which generates realistic random data, was used.
3. Initial transactions were processed in a preliminary round without time measurement. This step was necessary because the processing of first transactions can take slightly longer.
4. The time was measured for subsequent transactions. That was the main round of this benchmark.

Each transaction consisted of creating a random order, recording it in the DB, and updating the corresponding number of IMMVs. A total of 8 measurements were performed for each number of IMMVs ranging from 0 to 7, added in the order specified in the problem formulation.

The following parameters were used:

- Number of manufacturers: 25
- Number of products: 200
- Number of customers: 100
- Number of products in an order: 3
- Number of transactions in the initial round:

- Number of transactions in the main round:
2500
Indexes were created for all primary and foreign
keys.

During the experiment, all processor cores were
loaded to 40%, and PostgreSQL used 130 MB of RAM.
The obtained results are presented in Figure 2:

Figure 2. Dependence of transaction execution time on the number of IMMVs in the transactions.

The second stage of the experiment involved measuring the execution time of 1,000 selection queries for the first 10 rows of analytical data from IMMVs and from the base tables of that MV (using the base query). The data in the tables and IMMVs were carried over from the first stage of the experiment. The obtained results are presented in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Comparison of data retrieval speed using the base query versus IMMVs

Analysis of the results

Figure 2 shows that as the number of IMMVs updated within a transaction increases, the transaction processing time also increases linearly. In other words, adding a new IMMV to the transaction raises the processing time by a conditionally constant value. The variation in this value is primarily influenced by the complexity of calculating the necessary changes for each IMMV.

The increase of processing time is caused by distribution of all the necessary calculations for updating the IMMVs across transactions. The savings of time are clearly visible in Figure 3. Data retrieval from IMMVs is always faster than from executing the base query. For some IMMVs (e.g., the first and seventh), retrieval is more than 30 times faster. Moreover, the speed of data retrieval from IMMVs is independent of their creation complexity and happens in constant time.

Examples can be provided where the use of IMMVs becomes necessary. This happens in cases where real-time monitoring of a certain process is required. IMMVs are also essential when analytical data are queried very frequently or by many users simultaneously. Such cases may require less than 15 milliseconds for the base query execution.

The use of IMMVs is most beneficial in the following two scenarios:

- When analytical data are queried much more frequently than the base tables are updated, especially when calculating such data is resource-intensive;
- When, upon reaching a certain threshold, a specific action must be performed immediately, and updating the IMMV may be more advantageous than recalculating the entire condition, especially when the condition is complex.

In the previously conducted experiment with marketplace DB, examples of effective use of IMMVs include:

- The average order amounts for each buyer overall and each month (MVs 5 and 6) could be displayed in the user dashboard and queried frequently (e.g., every minute). It is better to store this amount and return it in $O(1)$ time than to constantly calculate it in $O(n)$ time, where n (the number of orders) grows.
- The total amounts of money for sold/purchased products each month for each manufacturer/buyer (MVs 1 and 2) can also be displayed in user dashboards. Additionally, when certain thresholds are reached, specific actions might be triggered (e.g., assigning a status or expanding system capabilities). After each order update, the total sum could be recalculated in $O(n)$ time, or the update could simply be added to the IMMV in $O(1)$ time and compared. The latter option is faster than the former one.

However, the use of IMMVs also has some drawbacks. One of the most critical drawbacks is the reduction of system fault tolerance. This reduction manifests in the following ways:

- Decreasing in the number of transactions processed per second (TPS rate). DB operations often be-

come the slowest element of the backend due to inefficient queries, improper indexing, etc. Adding incremental MV updates to transactions also requires optimization of such updates. Additionally, the maximum number of queries must be increased to ensure the system can handle peak loads.

- Increased likelihood of errors. Errors may occur during the programming of MV update, potentially causing inaccurate data in the MV or failure to process the entire transaction.

Other drawbacks include the high coupling between system components responsible for user interaction and analytics. Separating these components could have positive effects, as each component could perform its task independently, even on different computers.

For instance, analytical queries could be executed without slowing down transaction processing, and transactions could be processed without affecting analytics. If the system includes an analytics component built on an OLAP DBMS, analytical queries in it can be processed much faster (e.g., if the DBMS is columnar). This would increase the number of available analytical functions. However, the migration of data from OLTP to OLAP-based components would be necessary.

It is crucial that any optimization, such as IMMVs, be driven by necessity to avoid premature optimization. The final decision should rest with the developer, based on system requirements and the specific context.

Conclusions

Using IMMVs can improve query execution speed, but it can also slow down transaction processing and increase system complexity. Whether IMMVs should be implemented for specific queries depends on system requirements and usage patterns.

For frequently executed complex queries IMMVs can be beneficial despite their drawbacks. However, if analytical queries need to be performed without impacting transaction processing speed, it is advisable to separate the OLTP (transaction processing) and OLAP (analytical processing) components of the system.

Future research may focus on developing an automated system for working with IMMVs as a part of DB applications development [5], utilizing relational schema synthesis algorithms [6, 7, 9, 16], and applying IMMVs in the building of applications across various domains [17].

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